

Can we precisely measure the mass and size of a black hole simultaneously?

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Abstract

We studied the black hole in the context of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle and found that the mass and size of the black hole obey this principle, which hints at the measurement problem. Further, we derived its classical version, where the Planck constant is replaced by the universal gravitational constant; this is a new form of uncertainty relation. These two uncertainty relations may be used as a new criterion to define a black hole.

Black holes are mysterious objects that can eat all adjacent objects and grow bigger and more massive [1]. As it has been suggested, this black hole is an object that is not emitting anything, not even a single photon, which hinders our ability to get information about it [2]. However, there is no device to measure its dimensions, such as mass, size, temperature, and other related physical quantities [3].

Science advances, and we have some indirect ideas to quantify the mass and size of black holes, but it's difficult to say whether our measured quantities are precisely correct or not. In this line, in quantum mechanics, there is a theory about measurement called the Heisenberg uncertainty principle (HUP) [4], which is described below,

$$\nabla p \nabla r \geq h \quad (1)$$

where p is momentum and r is the position and h is Planck constant. In the context of this theory, we also argue that it may be valid for black holes since it is believed that black holes are quantum objects [5] [6].

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However, the question is, does this HUP come into play for a black hole's physical parameter determination? or, in other words, one can ask whether the determined parameters are precise or not. In this work, we will try to analyze this question and show whether this HUP is valid for black holes in same context or the others.

To meet this question, we study the black hole pressure which is due to quantum effect of a black hole [7], where it is denoted by the followings;

$$P = \frac{hc^9}{G^4 m^4} \quad (2)$$

where m is the mass of a black hole and c , G is speed of light and universal gravitational constant respectively.

It suggests pressure is inversely proportional to the quartic of the size of the black hole (where $r \sim Gm$). Since, this pressure is due to the entropic force of a black hole [8] [7], and it corresponds to the following:

$$F = \frac{h^2 c^2}{\nabla r^2 \nabla m^2 G} \quad (3)$$

where r is size of black hole.

Here, one can observe that the force is inversely proportional to the square of the size (radius of the black hole) and mass of the black hole. This force might also be due to the quantum effect of a quantum black hole.

However, by taking $F = \frac{c^4}{G}$ a constant entity therefore the Eq. (3) corresponds to the followings,

$$\nabla m \nabla r \geq h \quad (4)$$

this is similar to Eq. (1); however, the mass m and size of a black hole r are conjugate variables, so one can infer that there is an uncertainty relation between mass and the size of a black hole; that is, we can't measure the mass and size of a black hole simultaneously. This is the black hole's mass-size uncertainty relation and suggests both are conjugate variable.

It is worthy to mention that in preceding sections we showed that the mass and size of a black hole are conjugate variables, and there is a certain measurement uncertainty between both variables. This uncertainty is compatible with the Schwarzschild radius of a black hole; this can be shown by substituting r or m as the Planck length or mass in Eq. (4), and it gives us,

$$r \leq \frac{Gm}{c^2} \quad (5)$$

here we recovered the expression of Schwarzschild's radius. This suggests that the uncertainty relation is compatible with this radius.

This expression can also be deduced if we take the following condition,

$$\frac{c^4}{G} \leq \frac{Gm^2}{r^2}$$

it means to say, if the gravitational force of the any object is larger than the constant Planck force; we can get the Schwarzschild radius, at that stage the physical object will be a black hole like object.

Now, the Eq. (5) can be re-arranged as the followings,

$$\frac{\nabla r}{\nabla m} \leq \frac{G}{c^2} \quad (6)$$

it is similar to the Eq. (4), however, one can speculate that it shows the uncertainty relation in terms of the gravitational constant instead of the Planck constant. Therefore, its a gravitational uncertainty relation in classical mechanics and corresponds to the HUP.

An important aspect of this uncertainty relation, i.e., Eq. (4 and 6) is that it may be used as a new criterion for being a black hole. It means to say that if the mass, size, or radius of any matter corresponds to Eq. (4 and 6), that object will be a black hole-like object. This can be an alternative criterion for being a black hole-like object.

It also hints that if the condition, i.e., Eq. (4 and 6), is not satisfied, then it's not a black hole at all because it will not be compatible with the Schwarzschild radius, and at that condition, there might be an emission of particles or masses from a black hole. However, one can say that if the mass and size uncertainty relation is not satisfied, then there is a possibility of mass creation by a black hole. This might be an alternate approach to explaining the particle creation by a black hole.

In summary, the mass and size of a black hole are like conjugate variables of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle; however, we can't precisely measure both quantities simultaneously. Apart from it, similar to this uncertainty relation, we found a new form of uncertainty relation in terms of the universal gravitational constant, where the universal gravitational constant replaces the Planck constant. This might be the classical version of Heisenberg uncertainty principles. These uncertainty relations can be used as a new criterion for being a black hole.

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